

Kinetics and mechanism of ruthenium(III) chloride catalyzed oxidation of phosphorous acid by peroxomonosulfate in acetate buffers[†]

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The kinetics of oxidation of phosphorous acid by peroxomonosulfate in acetate buffers in the presence of ruthenium(III) chloride has been studied. The rate of disappearance of the peracid in the reaction has been observed to be zero order with respect to peroxomonosulfate. The proposed mechanism conforms to the rate law,

$$\frac{-d[\text{PMS}]}{dt} = k' = kK_d[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}][\text{H}^+]^{-1}$$

where k' is zero order rate constant. Thermodynamic parameters such as energy and entropy of activation have been calculated by conventional methods.

The oxidation of hypophosphorous acid in the redox step is the bimolecular interaction¹ of HSO_5^- and H_3PO_2 . However, the oxidation of phosphorous acid does not take place under identical experimental conditions. The kinetics studies of the oxidation of phosphorous acid by various oxidants, such as peroxodisulfate², Ce^{VI} ³, Cr^{VI} ⁴, Tl^{III} ⁵, Ag^{III} ⁶, MnO_4^- ^{7,8} and peroxodiphosphate⁹ have been reported. The oxidations by peroxodisulfate normally involve free radicals. In case of the oxidation by Ce^{VI} , kinetic as well as spectral evidences have been adduced¹⁰ for complexation and so as the complexation is reported in Cr^{VI} and phosphorous acid⁴. Since the reaction of peroxomonosulfate and phosphorous acid did not take place even at elevated temperatures, ruthenium(III) chloride was found to be an efficient catalyst for this reaction in acetate buffers. It is this ruthenium(III) catalysis that has prompted us to undertake the kinetics study of the title reaction from the following viewpoint.

First, since the oxidation of phosphorous acid does not occur under identical conditions of the oxidation of hypophosphorous acid, this necessitates to probe the reaction events in the former reaction to find a comparative pattern of reactivity of these acids towards peroxomonosulfate in a most precise manner.

Secondly, phosphorous acid was also chosen owing to the fact that (i) the system would be less complicated since the products of reduction of peroxomonosulfate and of oxidation of phosphorous acid would be SO_4^{2-} and PO_4^{3-} , respectively, (ii) no complexation of ruthenium(III) and phosphorous acid is reported and (iii) the reaction may shed some light on the role of tautomeric forms of phosphorous

acid as has been envisaged earlier.

Results and discussion

The concentration of peroxomonosulfate was varied in the range $(1.0-5.0) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients, viz. $[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3] = 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0$ and $5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, respectively, $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 1.0, 2.0$ and $5.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, respectively (Ru^{III} is heretofore written for RuCl_3) and $\text{pH} = 4.3$ (maintained by acetate buffers). The plots of $[\text{PMS}]_t$ against time were linear for more than two half-lives, indicating zero order dependence with respect to the oxidant. Thus the empirical rate eqn. (1) is obeyed at constant concentrations of the catalyst and the substrate,

$$\frac{-d[\text{PMS}]}{dt} = k' \quad (1)$$

where k' is zero order rate constant.

The concentration of phosphorous acid was varied from 1.0×10^{-3} to $10.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at constant concentrations of other reaction components, viz. $[\text{PMS}] = 2.0, 3.0,$ and $4.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, respectively, $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH} = 4.3$. The zero order rate constants were evaluated and the plot of rate constant against the concentration of phosphorous acid yielded a straight line passing through the origin conforming to first order dependence with respect to phosphorous acid.

The concentration of ruthenium(III) chloride was varied from 2.0 to $10.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients, viz. $[\text{PMS}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}$

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

dm^{-3} , $[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3] = 1.0$ and $2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, respectively, and $\text{pH} = 4.3$. The rate increases proportionately with increasing concentration of the catalyst as is confirmed by $\ln k'$ vs $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ that yields a straight line passing through the origin.

The pH of the reaction was varied from 3.05 to 4.75 at fixed concentrations of other reaction components, viz. $[\text{PMS}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at temperatures 25, 30 and 35°, respectively, by employing acetic acid at constant concentration of sodium acetate, the latter did not affect the rate of the reaction. The rate decreases with increasing hydrogen ion concentration or decreasing pH and conforms to an empirical rate law (2),

$$\frac{-d[\text{PMS}]}{dt} = \frac{A[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (2)$$

where A is an empirical constant.

The effect of ionic strength was studied by employing lithium perchlorate/sodium nitrate in the range 0.2–2.0 mol dm^{-3} at constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients, viz. $[\text{PMS}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH} = 4.3$. The rate remains unchanged with the changing ionic strength.

Similarly, benzene and *t*-butyl alcohol respectively also do not affect the rate eliminating the possibility of any involvement of OH and SO_4^{\ominus} free radicals. Further, the participation of free radicals was also ruled out on the premise that the monomer acrylic acid on the addition into reaction mixture did not polymerize.

It has been shown for a large number of reactions of trivalent phosphorus that phosphorus nucleophiles attack the oxidant. Nucleophilic attack of the phosphorus nucleophile: $\text{P}(\text{OH})_3$ by chlorine is reported¹¹. The evidence for the formation of $\text{P}(\text{OH})_3$ tautomer has been provided by Martin¹² in the studies of phosphonate-phosphite equilibria and also in the H_3PO_3 - I_2 reaction¹³. Silver(II) oxidation of H_3PO_3 has also been explained⁶ by proposing the involvement of the tautomer.

Peroxomonosulfate is considered to be a strong oxidant and probably it is this reason that the oxidant has been employed in a wider range of oxidation reactions^{14–20}. Thus far two major modes of oxidation have been reported and the most common among them is two-electron transfer of terminal peroxy oxygen from the per-acid. However, the least observed mode of oxidation is via free radical (SO_4^{\ominus}) formation and is reported²¹ only in case of oxidation of vanadium(IV) by peracid.

Peroxomonosulfuric acid has two ionizable protons – one is the sulfuric acid proton and the other that of hydrogen peroxide. The $\text{p}K_a$ of the sulfuric acid proton lies in the high acidity region and that of the H_2O_2 proton is 9.4²². The reactions of peracid in general exhibit acid catalysis. The inverse acid dependence is not unique in the sense that the reaction has been carried out in moderate acidic pH region. If nucleophilic attack by peroxide²³ is taken into account, SO_5^{2-} species should be more reactive than HSO_5^- . Nevertheless, evidences of strong nucleophilic character of peroxides have been adduced^{24,25}.

So far phosphorus acid species are concerned, phosphite would exist as H_3PO_3 and H_2PO_3^- if pH is any guide in these reactions :

K_d^1 and K_d^2 are the first^{26,27} and second²⁸ dissociation constants of phosphorus acid and are reported to be 0.076 mol dm^{-3} and $7.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, respectively.

In case of ruthenium(III) catalyzed reactions, different catalyst redox cycles such as Ru^{III} - Ru^{I} ,^{29,30} and Ru^{III} - Ru^{IV} ^{31,32} are reported. Since order with respect to peroxy-monosulfate is zero, the oxidant, therefore, should not be the part of the rate-controlling step. Thus, hydrogen ion dependence cannot be correlated to peracid. If pH is taken into account, eqm. (3) appears to be predominant indicating H_2PO_3^- to be the reactive form of the phosphorous acid. Therefore, the reaction events can be accounted for the mechanism proposed as follows :

Mechanism-I :

Table-1 (contd.)

$H_2PO_3^+ + H_2O \xrightarrow{\text{Fast}} H_3PO_4 + H^+$	(10)	5.0	5.0	1.0	1.42	28.4	
where, $L = Cl_2$, $m = 2$ and $n = 2$ for Ru^{III} ion.		1.0	.0	2.0	0.46	26.0	
The loss of peracid leads to rate law (11) or (12),		2.0	1.0	2.0	0.48	26.5	
$\frac{-d[PMS]}{dt} = \frac{k_1'K_1'K_d'[H_3PO_3][Ru^{III}L(H_2O)_{6-m}]^{(n-3)-}}{[H^+]}$	(11)	3.0	1.0	2.0	0.50	26.0	
or $k = k_1'K_1'K_d'/[H^+]$		4.0	1.0	2.0	0.54	27.0	
or $k = k_1K_d'/[H^+]$	(12)	5.0	1.0	2.0	0.54	27.0	
Since the equilibrium constant K_1' is very small, $k_1 = k_1'K_1'$.		6.0	1.0	2.0	0.58	29.0	
The values of observed second order rate constant (k) are collected in Table 1.		8.0	1.0	2.0	0.58	29.0	
		9.0	1.0	2.0	0.54	27.0	
		10.0	1.0	2.0	0.54	27.0	
		1.0	2.0	2.0	1.1	27.0	
		1.5	2.0	2.0	1.1	27.0	
		2.0	2.0	2.0	1.16	28.0	
		2.5	2.0	2.0	1.16	28.0	
		3.0	2.0	2.0	1.16	28.0	
		3.5	2.0	2.0	1.16	28.0	
		4.0	2.0	2.0	1.20	28.5	
		4.5	2.0	2.0	1.20	28.5	
		5.0	2.0	2.0	1.20	28.5	
		1.0	3.0	2.0	1.60	28.6	
		2.0	3.0	2.0	1.66	27.6	
		3.0	3.0	2.0	1.66	27.6	
		4.0	3.0	2.0	1.66	27.6	
		5.0	3.0	2.0	2.0	28.5	
		1.0	4.0	2.0	2.16	27.0	
		2.0	4.0	2.0	2.16	27.0	
		3.0	4.0	2.0	2.30	28.6	
		4.0	4.0	2.0	2.50	28.6	
		5.0	4.0	2.0	2.50	28.6	
		1.0	5.0	2.0	2.58	26.0	
		2.0	5.0	2.0	2.60	26.0	
		3.0	5.0	2.0	2.70	27.0	
		3.5	5.0	2.0	2.90	29.0	
		4.0	5.0	2.0	2.90	29.0	
		4.5	5.0	2.0	2.90	29.0	
		5.0	2.0	5.0	1.25	26.0	
		1.0	4.0	1.0	5.0	1.20	26.0
		2.0	4.0	1.0	5.0	1.16	26.0
		3.0	4.0	1.0	5.0	1.25	26.0
		3.5	4.0	1.0	5.0	1.42	28.4
		4.0	4.0	1.0	5.0	1.42	28.4
		4.5	4.0	1.0	5.0	1.16	26.0
		5.0	4.0	1.0	5.0	1.25	26.0
		2.0	5.0	1.0	10.0	0.51	26.0
		3.0	5.0	1.0	10.0	0.62	26.0
		3.5	5.0	1.0	10.0	0.85	28.0
		4.0	5.0	1.0	10.0	0.95	27.0
		4.5	5.0	1.0	10.0	1.10	27.5

Table-1 (contd.)

2.0	0.50	10.0	0.35	26.0
2.0	0.60	10.0	1.66	27.6
2.0	0.80	10.0	2.16	27.0
2.0	1.00	10.0	2.75	27.5
3.0	0.10	10.0	0.28	28.0
3.0	0.20	10.0	0.52	26.0
3.0	0.25	10.0	0.71	28.3
3.0	0.30	10.0	0.85	28.3
3.0	0.35	10.0	1.0	28.5
3.0	0.40	10.0	1.15	28.5
3.0	0.50	10.0	1.40	28.0
3.0	0.60	10.0	0.77	28.5
3.0	0.80	10.0	2.30	28.5
3.0	1.00	10.0	2.80	28.0
4.0	0.10	10.0	0.28	28.0
4.0	0.20	10.0	0.56	28.0
4.0	0.25	10.0	0.71	28.3
4.0	0.30	10.0	0.83	27.6
4.0	0.35	10.0	1.01	28.5
4.0	0.40	10.0	1.15	28.7
4.0	0.60	10.0	1.70	28.3
4.0	0.80	10.0	2.08	26.0
4.0	1.0	10.0	2.77	27.7
2.0	1.0	2.0	0.60	26.0
2.0	1.0	4.0	1.06	26.5
2.0	1.0	5.0	1.30	26.0
2.0	1.0	6.0	1.66	27.6
2.0	1.0	8.0	2.30	28.7
2.0	1.0	10.0	2.70	27.0
2.0	2.0	2.0	1.08	27.0
2.0	2.0	3.0	1.66	27.6
2.0	2.0	4.0	2.29	28.0
2.0	2.0	5.0	2.70	27.0
2.0	2.0	6.0	3.33	27.7
2.0	2.0	8.0	4.16	27.7
2.0	2.0	10.0	5.42	26.0
2.0	2.0	1.0	0.60	26.0
4.0	4.0	1.0	1.13	28.2
6.0	6.0	1.0	1.60	26.6
8.0	8.0	1.0	2.10	26.2
10.0	10.0	1.0	2.60	26.0

This rate law accounts for an inverse hydrogen ion dependence exhibiting a straight line passing through the origin in a plot of k vs $1/[H^+]$. Further ' k_1K_d ' were calculated to be 5.2×10^{-1} , 7.5×10^{-1} and $13.2 \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ from the gradient at 25, 30 and 35°, respectively, and $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Alternatively, if H_3PO_3 is considered to be the reactive form of phosphorus acid towards the species of the catalyst

governed by hydrolytic equilibria of the catalyst, Mechanism-II can also account for the experimental observations.

Mechanism-II :

The loss of peroxomonosulfate leads to rate law (21),

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{-d[PMS]}{dt} \\ &= k_1''[Ru^{III}(H_3PO_3)] + k_2''[Ru^{III}(H_2PO_3)^-] \\ &= \left(k_1''K_1'' + \frac{k_2''K_hK_2''}{[H^+]} \right) [Ru^{III}][H_3PO_3] \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Substituting the gross analytical concentration of ruthenium(III) in eqn. (21), eqn. (22) is obtained,

$$\frac{-d[PMS]}{dt} = \left(k_1''K_1'' + \frac{k_2''K_hK_2''}{[H^+]} \right) \frac{[Ru^{III}][H_3PO_3][H^+]}{[H^+] + K_h + K_1''([H^+] + K_2'')[H_3PO_3]} \quad (22)$$

Since the order with respect to phosphorous acid is one, K_1'' , K_2'' and K_h are small equilibrium constants, the inequality $[H^+] \gg (K_h + K_1''([H^+] + K_2'')[H_3PO_3])$ is, therefore, valid. This further reduces the rate laws (22) to (23) or (24),

$$\frac{-d[PMS]}{dt} = \left(k_1''K_1'' + \frac{k_2''K_hK_2''}{[H^+]} \right) [Ru^{III}][H_3PO_3] \quad (23)$$

$$\text{or } k'' = \left(k_1''K_1'' + \frac{k_2''K_hK_2''}{[H^+]} \right) \quad (24)$$

Since the plot of k'' vs $[H^+]^{-1}$ yields a straight line passing through the origin, $(k_1''K_1'')$ term in rate eqn. (24) is negligible as compared to $k_2''K_hK_2''$.

There is also a third possibility of accounting for the experimental results and Mechanism-III can be proposed by considering both molecular and dissociated forms of the phosphorus acid to be the reactive forms,

Mechanism-III :

Such a mechanism leads to the rate law (30),

$$\frac{-d[\text{PMS}]}{dt} = \left(k_3 K' + \frac{k_4 K'' K_d}{[\text{H}^+]} \right) \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}][\text{H}^+]}{([\text{H}^+] + k_d)} \quad (30)$$

Since the order with respect to phosphorous acid is one and equilibrium constants K' and K'' are very small and the plot of rate vs $[\text{H}^+]$ yields a straight line passing through the origin, this reduces the rate laws (30) to (31) or (32),

$$\frac{-d[\text{PMS}]}{dt} = \frac{k'' K' K_d [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}][\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3]}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (31)$$

$$\text{or } k' = \frac{k'' K' K_d}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (32)$$

where, k' is an observed second order rate constant. The absence of general acid catalysis as is reported in other reactions of phosphorous acid is worth-mentioning. The high charge on Ru^{III} appears to induce rupture of P-H bond more readily than the attack of the proton on unprotonated oxygen of -P-O.

The energy of activation for the slow step was calculated by employing conventional method to be $(54 \pm 2) \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The entropy of activation was calculated to be $(40 \pm 4) \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ by employing the eqn.³³ (33),

$$k = (ekT/h) \exp \Delta S^\ddagger/R \exp(-E_a^\ddagger/RT) \quad (33)$$

Since the ionization of the P-H bond in H_3PO_3 is not favourable, peroxomonosulfate in all probability appears to attack phosphorous acid directly, the P-H bond is broken in the rate-controlling step. The slow step may assign hydride ion transfer to the oxidant.

The attack of HSO_5^- on the phosphorus atom to form a peroxide bridge with five-coordinate phosphorus is another possibility. The transfer of an electron pair through the bridge occurs with concomitant proton transfer to the solvent.

However, Schemes 1 and 2 are kinetically indistinguishable.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Experimental

Sodium monohydrogen phosphite ($\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (AnalaR) was used as received. Ruthenium trichloride hydrate (Johnson and Matthey) was purified by evaporation with conc. HCl. Its solution was prepared in HCl (0.3 mol dm^{-3}) eliminating the traces of Ru^{IV} by treating with mercury³⁴. The solution was allowed to stay for a longer period to attain equilibrium and was tested³⁵ negative with iodide for Ru^{IV} . This solution was standardized³⁶ and stored in glass vessels painted black from the outside at refrigerated temperature ($\sim 5^\circ$).

Acetate buffers were employed as the reaction media and lithium perchlorate/sodium nitrate was used for adjustment or variation of the ionic strength. Since acetate ions do not affect the rate of the reaction, pH variation was made by varying the concentration of acetic acid in acetate-buffers. pH was measured on a ECIL pH meter with the maximum variation of ± 0.01 unit.

Kinetics of the reactions were studied by taking reaction mixtures in glass-stoppered Erlenmeyer flasks in a thermostated water-bath ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) unless mentioned otherwise. Kinetics were monitored iodometrically by assaying the oxidant at different time intervals in aliquots of the reaction mixture (5 or 10 cm^3). Initial rates were computed employing plane-mirror method³⁷. Pseudo-first order rate constants were also evaluated wherever reaction conditions permitted (excess of H_3PO_3). The triplicate rate measurements were reproducible to within $\pm 5\%$.

A slow reaction between iodine and phosphorus acid is reported³⁷ under the acid conditions employed, and during the time titration was carried out, no such reaction occurred. Trace impurities, such as Cu^{2+} and Fe^{3+} generally present in the reagents, were also found to have no effect on the rate of the reaction.

The reaction products SO_4^{2-} and PO_4^{3-} or phosphoric acid neither interfered with the analytical methods nor with the method employed for monitoring the kinetics. This was confirmed by undertaking a few reactions for kinetics in their presence over the time and temperature range chosen for the study of the main reaction.

Stoichiometry : Phosphorous acid and peroxomonosulfate of different concentrations in acetate buffers were allowed to react at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in a thermostated water-bath for ca. ~ 6 h. The concentration of HSO_5^- or H_3PO_3 , whichever was in excess, was determined. HSO_5^- and phosphorous acid were determined iodometrically and cerimetrically³⁸ respectively. One mole of phosphorus acid is required for each mole of HSO_5^- corresponding to the reaction,

Phosphoric acid could not be determined owing to the presence of both acetic acid and phosphorous acid as there is no known method of determination which is free of interferences. However, the qualitative test³⁹ confirmed the absence of H_3PO_3 when the latter was in sufficiently lesser concentration than that of peroxomonosulfate.

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